

Digital Competencies of Cataloguers for Organization of Information Resources in Ramat Library University Maiduguri, Borno State

Fatima Umar Faruq¹

Aliyu Shehu Yakubu²

Umar Abba³

^{1, 2} Department of Library and Information Science, Faculty of Education, University of Maiduguri.

³ Ramat Library University of Maiduguri

¹ fatimaumarfaruq00@unimaid.edu.ng,

² kafintafawa2@unimaid.edu.ng,

³ uabba771@unimaid.edu.ng

Abstract

Background: This study explores the digital competencies of cataloguers in organizing information resources at Ramat Library, University of Maiduguri, as well as the challenges faced during the process.

Methodology: A quantitative research approach using a survey design was adopted. Self-designed questionnaires were distributed to all nine cataloguers at Ramat Library, employing total enumeration sampling due to the manageable population size. Only eight questionnaires were returned and analysed. Data was processed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), with frequency counts, mean scores, and standard deviation applied for analysis. Results were presented in tables.

Findings/Results: Findings revealed that most respondents had low digital competency levels in organizing information resources. While the majority of identified resources were being catalogued, inadequate funding, insufficient training, and unreliable power supply were key obstacles hindering effective cataloguing and organization.

Implications: The study highlights the need for enhanced digital skills development and improved infrastructure to optimize information resource management in academic libraries.

Conclusion: The cataloguers' limited digital competencies and institutional challenges significantly impede efficient information organization at Ramat Library.

Recommendations: Periodic training and workshops should be provided to enhance cataloguers' digital skills. Additionally, adequate funding should be allocated to procure necessary facilities and address power supply issues.

Keywords: Digital Competencies, Cataloguers, Organization, Information Resources, University of Maiduguri

Introduction

Digital Competence is the possession of digital skills and the ability to actively use the skills by librarians in the library. Digital competencies for cataloguers involve a range of skills which include but are not limited to metadata creation, digital resource description, knowledge of cataloguing, proficiency in integrated library systems (ILS) and digital repository management. Furthermore, cataloguers as a matter of fact should have an understanding of evolving technologies such as artificial intelligence, linked data, and automation tools to enhance discoverability and accessibility of library information resources (Sibiya & Chuma, 2022).

Librarianship is a profession that points organization of information resources as one of the key functions of the library. The priority of any librarian is to acquire, organize, preserve and facilitate easy access to relevant information resources needed for individual consultation, therefore cataloguers are expected to have competence in their field of specialization for the accomplishment of the library objectives. Organization of information resources is the process of proper description of books, journals, audio-visual materials etc for easy identification, location and retrieval of all kinds of resources. The cataloguers' activities encompass a complete bibliographic description of a record or a document. Cataloguers found the library's technical activities, operations and services easily in this 21st century because of the digital age. However, cataloguers with digital competency enhance the effective organization of information resources which enables

users to have access to documented information and utilize them accurately, effectively and easily. Abdul, Usman, Ibrahim, and Moh'd, (2020). Opine that enhancing uniformity has made it possible for cataloguers to describe the bibliographic details in the format of information resources of similar or the same manner with the required standards for the information resources of such format. In other words, improving uniformity and consistency made cataloguers to be competent in describing the bibliographic details of all kinds of information resources.

The Digital Competence of cataloguers is influenced by technological advancement specifically in this digital era. Cataloguers' digital competency is the ability to possess quality and suitable task enrolment in library operations and services. Competent cataloguers simplified the process of organizing information resources to reduce time consumption and facilitate easy and speedy technical services in the libraries, while the lack of this competence and skills reverses the case. In a similar study of Technology from Sage (2023), it was reported that cataloguing or organization of information and knowledge was rated contemporary to the skills/competence of 17th out of the 32 librarians. Organizing information in the digital era is so challenging mostly in Nigerian libraries due to many factors like insufficient Internet bandwidth, inadequate digital skills of library personnel, technological anxiety, wrong perceptions of the impact of technology on library activities, inadequate ICT infrastructure and technological obsolescence. With the above authors' view, this can affect cataloguers' competence in the library.

Numerous studies such as Sibiya and Chuma, (2022), CIn, (2016) and David, West and Angrey, (2018) have highlighted the importance of digital skills among information professionals, especially, in the context of ensuring seamless information retrieval, interoperability of library systems, and accessibility of resources. However, gaps remain in the professional development and training of cataloguers, as many traditional cataloguing practices have yet to fully integrate with emerging digital standards. Correspondingly, a feasibility study by the researchers on digital competence of cataloguers in the, Ramat Library University of Maiduguri, indicated that they need more training and modern infrastructure. Challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, inadequate ICT facilities, inadequate database, minimal cataloguers' competence/skills

in system analysis, minimal competence of classification and assigning metadata, minimal competence of digitization process, minimal competence of web navigation, minimal competence of searching techniques and virtual reference services are the main causes of their incompetence. Therefore, this study tends to investigate the extent of the digital competence of cataloguers in organizing information resources in the Ramat Library University of Maiduguri.

Problem Statements

It is unanimously agreed that cataloguing is one of the fundamental tasks that support seamless retrieving of information resources and enhance services of the libraries. In this technological advancement era, libraries are transitioning from traditional cataloguing approaches to computerized and digital ones (Sibiya & Chuma, 2022). Effective cataloguing services are indispensable for organizing, assembling and retrieving library information resources efficiently. However, the digital competency of librarians remains a serious challenge in warranting the effective implementation and utilization of digital cataloguing tools. Many librarians may have inadequate training in digital cataloguing software, metadata standards and integrated library systems (ILS). This gap in digital skills can lead to inefficiencies, errors in cataloguing, and difficulty in maintaining up-to-date and accessible library information resources. Furthermore, inadequate needed facilities, regular power outage, poor internet connectivity and insufficient funding may contribute toward cataloguers' incompetency while discharging their duties. Additionally, rapid technological advancements require continuous professional development, which some libraries have not been prioritize and give it serious attention. Consequently, it has been acknowledged that insufficient digital competency among librarians can result in poor cataloguing practices, affecting users' ability to locate and access information resources efficiently (Atanda, 2021). Therefore, this study intends to assess the digital competency of cataloguers in organizing information resources at Ramat library, identifying information resources they catalogue and assess some challenges that affect their digital skill on cataloguing services.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the level of digital competencies required by cataloguers for organizing information resources in the Universities in Ramat Library University of Maiduguri
2. Identify the types of information resources organized by cataloguers in the library
3. identify the challenges associated with the acquisition of digital competencies in the Ramat Library University of Maiduguri

Research Questions

1. What is the level of required digital competence of cataloguers in organizing information resources?
2. What types of information resources are organized by cataloguers in the library?
3. What are the challenges associated with the acquisition of digital competencies in the Ramat Library University of Maiduguri

Literature Review

Igere (2022) opined that the digital era has made proper management of information resources easier and simpler which has culminated in the efficiency of meeting the information needs of patrons in libraries. David, West and Angrey (2018) reported that the use of digital information tools in libraries and information centres demands the technical competencies of librarians to successfully navigate through digital information. Sibiya and Chuma, (2022) pointed out that digital management skills refer to the ability of librarians to organize, implement, and maintain digital tools and work in computerized environments.

Mariano, (2024) reported that the global change now in libraries has tremendously replaced how libraries render their services. Librarians now have more roles and

responsibilities as a result of the shift from a print to a digital environment. They are now responsible for the research outcomes of their institutions and the community at large, as well as teaching students' information retrieval skills in the digital environment. The digital environment makes information access cheap and freely available. Reference tools, automated journals, and digital documentation of historical materials now come in a variety of packages from different online publishers and are readily available.

Mendez (2019) stated that institutional librarians' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and digital skills are needed in digital information systems. Users' need for e-information services is likewise expanding and increasingly becoming crucial. The rise of digital technology is changing conventional caretakers of physical collections into online information content creators. When physical libraries close, librarians are involved in providing online information services to the general population. The emerging internet technology has constantly connected to better accurate digital services to library users and provides concrete outcomes. Similarly, Joel and Ibrahim (2021) stated that librarians as information professionals are expected to demonstrate digital competencies in order to thrive in the digital environment to energetically and vigorously lead in the procurement or acquisition for application, utilization, and implementation of modern technologies to improve library and information services.

Genette and Piper, (2022) stated that the Organization of information has expanded to cover the description of digital resources such as e-books, online databases, websites, and multimedia content. Moreover, it encompasses the process of organizing and describing information resources in a digital environment. Traditionally, cataloguing involved creating records for physical resources within libraries. Abdul, Usman, Ibrahim and Moh'd (2020) also reported that digitization has a major impact on cataloguing by creating new information resources and new forms of communication.

According to Kamba (2020) is a global era surrounded by technological applications which refers to the products of information technology consisting of design, advanced development, accomplishment, support, or administration of computers, foundation of information systems, mostly software application and computer hardware. It works with

the use of electronic computers and computer software to renovate, defend, develop and broadcast information.

Onuoha and Chukwueke (2022) supported the views that inadequate funding of library technical operations, inadequate technological facilities, inadequate technology perception of cataloguers and classifiers in libraries, inadequate digital infrastructure, unstable power supply, frequent changes in technology, inadequate technical support, poor maintenance culture of technological facilities, changes in software applications in libraries, poor Internet bandwidth, management problems and lack of continual training of cataloguers are some factors mitigating the application of technologies for cataloguing and classification in libraries.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive research design which was suitable for the study. It aims to provide an accurate details description of the research study. Descriptive research design summarizes the characteristics of a population, phenomenon, or situation. The population of the study comprises of Nine (9) cataloguers in Ramat Library University of Maiduguri. A total enumeration sampling was employed for the study due to the fact that the population size is manageable. A five (5) Likert scale self-developed questionnaire was used for the collection of data from the respondents. The questionnaire was administered and retrieved within ten days after undergoing thorough validation by the experts. However, only eight questionnaires were returned and analyzed in this study. Descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentage scores, mean and standard deviation are used and the results are presented in tables.

Findings of the Study

Table 1: Competence of Cataloguers

Code	Statement	VHL	HL	ML	LL	ZL	Mean	Std Dev
DigCom1	I have competence in the use of MARC	0	2	2	3	1	2.625	1.060
DigCom2	I have competence in the use of OPAC	1	1	2	3	1	2.750	1.281
DigCom3	I have competence in the use of Catalogue database	1	1	2	3	1	2.750	1.281
DigCom4	I have competence in the use of metadata schema	1	1	2	3	1	2.375	0.916
DigCom5	I have competence in the use of OCL	0	1	2	4	1	6.625	1.060

Results from Table 1 indicated that two respondents have a high level of competency in cataloguing information resources, two have a moderate level of competency in organizing information resources, three respondents have only a low level of competency in organizing information resources, and one of the respondents acknowledges that he/she has zero competency in organizing information resources. On the use of OPAC, the majority of respondents, represented by three of them said that they have a low level of competence in the use of OPAC, followed by two respondents who said that they have a moderate level of competence in the use of OPAC, then one each who acknowledged that he has very high level, high level and zero level of competency in the use of OPAC respectively.

Moreover, this study's findings revealed that the majority of respondents represented by three of them confirmed that they have a low level of competency in the use of catalogue databases, followed by two of them who said that they have a moderate level of competency in the use of database and one each agreed that he/she has very high level, high level and zero level of competency in the use of catalogue database respectively.

On the use of metadata schema, the majority of respondents, represented by three of them, said that they have a low level of competence in the use of metadata schema, followed by two respondents who said that they have a moderate level of competence in the use of metadata schema, then one each who acknowledged that he has very high level, high level and zero level of competency in the use of metadata schema respectively. Additionally, on the use of OCL, the majority of the respondents, represented by four of them, acknowledged that they have low level of competency in its use, followed by two of them who said that they have moderate level of competency in the use of meta OCL and one each said he/she has high level and zero level of competency in the use of OCL respectively. From the general stands of this analysis, it is deduced that the respondents have a low level of digital competency in organizing and cataloguing information resources in the said library.

Objective 2.: To achieve this objective, nine items are asked to assess it and the results obtained indicated the extent to which each of the identified information resources are organize and catalogue in Ramat library as presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2. The Types of Information Resources Organize by Cataloguers in Ramat Library

Code	Statement	SA	A	UD	D	SD	Mean	Std Dev
InfRes1	Books	6	2	0	0	0	4.750	0.462
InfRes2	Journals	1	6	1	0	0	4.000	0.532
InfRes3	Magazines	1	5	2	0	0	3.875	0.640
InfRes4	CD Plates	1	4	2	1	0	3.625	0.916
InfRes5	Video	1	4	2	1	0	3.625	0.916
InfRes6	Sound Recorder	0	5	3	0	0	3.625	0.51
InfRes7	Thesis	4	4	0	0	0	4.500	0.534
InfRes8	Dissertation	4	4	0	0	0	4.500	0.534
InfRes9	Newspapers	3	2	1	1	0	4.000	1.069

From Table 2 above, it is revealed that six and two respondents strongly agree and agree respectively that they catalogue books as information resources in the library, while one and six respondents agree and strongly agree that they catalogue journals as information resources in the library. Only one respondent is undecided on the cataloguing of journals

as an information resource. Moreover, five and one respondents agreed and strongly agreed, respectively, that they catalogue and organize magazines in the library, while two of them remained neutral on the statement. On the organization and cataloguing of CD plates, four and one respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that they organize and catalogue them as information resources, while two of them remained undecided and one of them disagreed that he/she organizes and catalogues CD plates in the library.

Additionally, regarding the organization and cataloguing of the videos, four and one respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that they organize and catalogue videos in the library while two of them remained undecided and one of them disagreed with that statement. While five respondents agreed that they organize and catalogue sound recordings in the library, three of them remained quiet about this statement. On the organization and cataloguing of the thesis in the library, four respondents strongly agree likewise four respondents agree with the statement, indicating that none has an objection that they organize and catalogue the thesis in the library.

Organization and cataloguing of a dissertation are another question that was asked in this research, therefore, four each strongly agreed and disagreed respectively that they organize and catalogue dissertations in the library which also indicated that none of the respondents has objection to organizing and cataloguing dissertations in the said library. Lastly, regarding the organization and cataloguing of the newspapers, three and two respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively that they organize and catalogue newspapers in the library while four respondents disagreed and another one remained neutral that they organize and catalogue newspapers in the library. From the cumulative results, it is evident that the majority of respondents agreed and strongly agreed that they organize and catalogue the identified information resources in the Ramat library.

Table 3. Challenges Associated with the Acquisition of Digital Competencies in the Ramat Library

Code	Statement	SA	A	UD	D	SD	Mean	Std Dev
Chall1	Lack of library software packages adoption	5	3	0	0	0	4.625	0.517
Chall2	Poor encouragement from the management	6	2	0	0	0	4.750	0.462
Chall3	Inadequate staff training	6	2	0	0	0	4.750	0.462
Chall4	Inadequate internet facilities	5	1	2	0	0	4.375	0.916
Chall5	Lack of sound perceptive digital cataloguers	5	3	0	0	0	4.625	0.517
Chall6	Inadequate infrastructural facilities	5	1	1	1	0	4.250	1.164
Chall7	Poor maintenance culture	5	1	2	0	0	4.375	0.916
Chall8	Inadequate power supply	6	2	0	0	0	4.750	0.462
Chall9	Inadequate funding	6	2	0	0	0	4.750	0.462

Regarding the challenges associated with the cataloguer’s level of digital competency, as seen in Table 3, a great proportion of respondents strongly agreed and agreed that non-adoption of library software, poor encouragement from the management, inadequate staff training, lack of internet facilities, lack of sound perceptive digital cataloguers, inadequate infrastructural facilities, poor maintenance culture, inadequate power supply and insufficient funding militate against cataloguers’ digital competency in organizing information resources in the library. Contrarily, a small proportion of respondents remained silent on these militating factors while only one respondent disagreed that inadequate infrastructural facilities militate against the cataloguer’s digital competency in the library. Based on this analysis, it is therefore concluded that all the identified militating factors negatively affect the digital competency of the respondents thus hindering effective cataloguing and organizing of information resources in Ramat library.

Discussion

Results of this study revealed that respondents have a low level of digital competency in organizing and cataloguing information resources as the majority of them responded. This

implies that insufficient digital competency will surely affect their capability to effectively and efficiently catalogue and organize digital information resources. Therefore, this calls for an urgent need for training and re-training of those respondents in order to be fully equipped with digital competency, especially in cataloguing and organizing information resources.

This finding coincided with that of Baryshev, Kasyanchuk, Tsvetochkina and Babina (2021) who also acknowledged that up to now many librarians don't have adequate digital skills to enable them to deliver efficient services. Likewise, the findings of Natařsa, Aleksandra, and Jelena (2020) supported this present finding as their results revealed that there is insufficient knowledge of modern technology among many librarians, especially in African countries. However, other findings which include that of (Atanda, 2021; Bass, 2019; Duran-riquelme & Flores-fernández, 2024) contradict these present findings as they all revealed that librarians in many academic libraries have sufficient knowledge of ICT and other forms of digital systems to cater for the 21st-century librarianship.

On the types of information resources organize by cataloguers in the Ramat library, it has been revealed by this study that all the identified information resources are catalogued and organized in the Ramat library though on different extents. This implies that the cataloguers are trying their best despite some challenges to catalogue and organize such information resources for enhancing the services of the library as also be seen from the Mean score of each information resource. However, more support can be needed to improve the system to be more efficient and effective than its present stage. This present finding agrees with other findings such as Gradin (2022) which revealed that almost all kinds of information resources are catalogued in Nigerian academic libraries. Moreover, Rockelle (2021) states that Nigerians are blessed with intelligent cataloguers who fully implement many cataloguing services correctly.

Additionally, Winifred, Beriliy and Fon (2023) confirms that information resources are catalogued and organize for efficient access and availability by users in many Nigerian universities. Contrarily to this present finding, Babina, Ermolovich, Bekuzarova (2022), revealed that insufficient facilities militate against the proper implementation of

cataloguing systems in some Nigerian academic libraries, thus calling for urgent attention on this aspect. Correspondingly, Kumari and Mishra (2020) revealed that some librarians found it difficult to properly organize and catalogue electronic information resources due to their nature of being soft copies and insufficient ICT knowledge of the librarians. Therefore, something needs to be done to improve the existing status of cataloguing services in such libraries.

Correspondingly, this research revealed that despite the opportunities that digital competency offers for cataloguing and organizing information resources, it is also associated with some challenges that include but are not limited to lack of internet facilities, lack of sound perceptive digital cataloguers, inadequate infrastructural facilities, poor maintenance culture, inadequate power supply, insufficient funding and insufficient staff training opportunities. These challenges and many more hinder the full implementation of cataloguing and organization of information resources. This therefore calls for immediate action that can improve the situation and bring more efficiency in the cataloguing services of the libraries. This present finding supported that of Tella and Odunola (2021) who reported that the adoption of novel technologies in Nigerian libraries is always associated with challenges that slow its adoption process. However, he justifies that some strategic efforts are underway toward curtailing such challenges in Nigeria. Moreover, Promise, Grace and Agu (2024) emphasized that library services are associated with some peculiar problems that hinder their smooth implementation for better service delivery. In the same vein, Monyela (2021) also found that cataloguing and organization of information resources are affected by many challenges that include many of those identified in this present finding.

Conclusion

This study examines the digital competence of cataloguers in organizing information resources at the Ramat Library, University of Maiduguri. The research explores the level of digital skills among cataloguers, the tools and technologies employed, and the challenges they face in ensuring efficient information organization. The study concludes that enhancing digital competence among cataloguers is crucial for efficient information resource management. Digital literacy directly impacts the effectiveness of cataloguing

practices, ensuring seamless access to information resources. Addressing training gaps, adopting modern library technologies, and integrating user-friendly metadata standards will significantly improve cataloguing efficiency. By adopting these measures, the Ramat Library, University of Maiduguri, can enhance its cataloguing operations, ultimately improving information accessibility and service delivery to users.

Recommendations

1. Based on the outcome of this study, it is deduced that the respondents have a low level of digital competency in organizing and cataloguing information resources in the said library. Therefore, it is recommended that the cataloguers should have periodic training and workshops that can equip them with more knowledge and competency of using digital means of cataloguing and organization of knowledge. This will solve the issue of having low digital competency that they currently experiencing as revealed in this study.
2. From the cumulative results for research question one which aims to address objective one, it is evident that the majority of respondents agreed and strongly agreed that they organize and catalogue the identified information resources in the Ramat library. Therefore, it is recommended more information resources should be verified as to whether they are being catalogued and organized at the library or not. Even the ones identified here, their mode of cataloguing and organization should be improved using more strategies.
3. Results also revealed that all the identified militating factors negatively affect the digital competency of the respondents thus hindering effective cataloguing and organizing of information resources in Ramat library. Therefore, it is recommended that immediate steps need to be taken to address the challenges that hinder many cataloguers from efficiently discharging their roles to improve service delivery. Doing so will significantly improve the cataloguing services in particular and that of the entire library at large.

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